

ISSUES OF HISTORICAL AND MODERN FORMS OF BUSINESS TERMS

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Abstract. *The field of terminology is one of the most urgent issues of linguistics, and this field has an ancient history. As each science or field develops, it can be observed that the terms and terms in it change and update. This article highlights some issues of historical and modern forms of business terms. The change of business terms over time is also shown in the following article.*

Keywords: *term, terminology, historical business terms, modern business terms.*

INTRODUCTION

Business terms are not new issues in today's linguistics field. Because many terms expressing the business concept have a very ancient history and stages of development. Let's talk about terms and terminology before business terms. The word "term" is derived from the Latin word "terminus", which means limit, limit, and it refers to the concept of a special field of knowledge or activity. is a representative word or phrase. Terminology is defined as a set of terms interacting with the system of concepts of a particular science. Any system of concepts corresponds to a certain system of terms. It is worth mentioning that terminological systems develop together with the progress of science and are constantly changing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Many scientists, especially in Russian linguistics, have carried out significant work on the issue of terminology. V.P.Danilenko, X.Xyuell, O.Vinokur, A.S.Gerd, O.S.Axmanova, D.S.Lotte, A.Mol, A.A.Reformatskiy, E.D.Polivanov, M.Pavlova, A.N.Tixonov, L.L.Kim, S.A.Tixonov, S.V.Grinev, V.N.Kim, T.S.Kim, A.D.Xayutin, S.V.Grinyo'v Kim, A.D. Khayutin, S.V. Grinyov and many other great scientists conducted research in the field of terminology and added their noticeable contribution to the science of terminology. We can observe several scientific and practical works of Uzbek terminologists too. Uzbek terminologists who conducted research in the field of terminology are U. Tursunov, A. Madvaliyev, H. Dadaboyev, A. Khojiyev, H. Khasanov, N. Ikromova, Ismailov, Ishayev, H. Hamidiy, SH. Abdullayeva, S. A number of scientists and linguists such as Ibrahimova, O. Usman, Kh. Professor Renat Doniyorov is one of the scientists who made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek language terminology. His book "Some issues of the technical terminology of the Uzbek language (1977) contains issues such as regulating the technical terminology of the Uzbek language and preventing a number of confusions in it. This work can be considered to be a significant contribution to the research of technical terminology. Many terminological dictionaries of the Uzbek language were compiled and published in the 30s of the 20th century. In this process, theoretical issues about the history of terms, meaning and subject groups of terms, grammatical structure and construction, development path and sources of enrichment were also developed [1.150] One of the first, Ulug Tursunov, clarified the issues of the terminology of the Uzbek language made efforts to enter. He also wrote a number of works dedicated to this issue. Some noticeable works on this topic are as following: "Til – terminologiyada burjuaziya intilishlariga qarshi", "O'zbek terminologiyasi masalalari",

“Terminologiya masalalari”, “O‘zbek adabiy tilida so‘z – terminlar tanlash prinsiplari” (“Language - against the aspirations of the bourgeoisie in terminology”, "Issues of Uzbek terminology", "Issues of terminology", "Principles of choosing words - terms in the literary language of Uzbek"). In these works, various views and concepts in the field of term creation, collection, regulation, unification and publication are discussed. In addition, he emphasized that the confusions that have occurred and are occurring in the field of terminology are beginning to be clearly visible.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSIONS

Admittedly, only business professionals can understand some business concepts. It is known that each field has its own terms and concepts, which can be well distinguished only by the skilled owners of their profession. They can also understand the historical stages of these terms.

The following table presents the historical and modern views of some terms related to business.

t/r	Historical trading concepts	Modern trading concepts
1	Merchant	merchant, trader, businessman
2	‘Mol’	goods, merchandise
3	Caravan	cargo, leasing, transport
4	Camel	transport, truck
5	‘Aqcha’	money, cash, plastic card, credit card
6	‘Tanga’	money, cash, plastic card, credit card
7	Debt	debt, credit
8	Consumer	buyer, consumer
9	income	Income
10	‘Chayqovchi’	Dealer
11	Trade	sales, online sales, marketing
12	Saving	economy
13	‘xazina, g’azna’	bank, account number
14	Losing money	bankruptcy
15	Shed	Shed
16	Purse	plastic card, credit card, wallet

If we pay attention to the words given in the table, we can see that some words are still used in this situation and some are completely new terms and new concepts. For example, instead of the concept of money, we can clearly see that the various terms used today, such as income, account number, wallet, credit card, plastic card, have changed and developed together with this field of business terms over time. A change in these terms greatly affects their meaning. We can also see that the terms representing vehicles are closely related to the invention of these vehicles. The invention of a new object is named according to the characteristics of this object and causes the introduction of a new term in the field of linguistics.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that such periodic changes in the field of terminology occur not only with business terms, but also in all areas. For example, the development of terms related to

the field of education is a proof of huge changes in this field. The new appearance and new names of methods, subjects, textbooks, classrooms or educational tools are proof of the continuous development of the language.

Turning to business terms, modern words and expressions are almost not translated, that is, such terms are accepted as borrowed words. Moreover, they have the same meaning, and it is no exaggeration to say that this situation is partly a part of the globalization process. Because the words used internationally have the same form and meaning. However, we can still find that national words and phrases are widely used in the field of nationalities and their linguistics.

REFERENCES

1. Gaziyeva Maftuna, Pirmatova Dilorom TERMINOLOGIK LUG'ATLAR HAMDA ULARNING AFZALLIKLARI XUSUSIDA. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. 1-5-betlar.
2. Odiljonovich, Hasanov Elyorjon. "The Issue Of Business Terms Used In English." *Journal of Positive School Psychology* 6.11 (2022): 3075-3081.
3. Odiljonovich, Hasanov Elyorjon. "A STUDY OF ADOPTED BUSINESS TERMS FROM ENGLISH INTO THE UZBEK LANGUAGE." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.12 (2022): 401- 403.
4. Shoabduraxmonov Sh. O'zbek adabiy tili va xalq shevalari –T.: 1960
5. <file:///C:/Users/OrgTechSERVICE/Downloads/termin-va-terminologiya-berilgan-ta-riflar.pdf>
6. Radjapov, E. (2022). *Sobirjon Oxunjonov. O'zbekiston.*
7. Radjapov, E. (2021). *Fayzulla Norxo'jayev. O'zbekistonning Eng Yangi Tarixi Masalalari bo'yicha Muvofiqlashtiruvchi-Metodik Markaz.*
8. Radjapov, E. (2021). *Turkiston mintaqasida milliy qo'shin shakllantirishda turk harbiy mutaxassilarining ishtiroki.*
9. Radjapov, E. (2020). *"Temir general". O'zbekiston Tarixi.*
10. Раджапов, Э. Г. (2018). ВОЕННАЯ ПОЛИТИКА СОВЕТСКАЯ ВЛАСТЬ В ПРИГОТОВЛЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЙ РАЗМЕЖЕВАНИЕ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (1), 17-23.
11. Haydarova, G. Traditions And Peculiarities Of Alisher Navoi In The Uzbek Ghazal Of The Xx Century. *The American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 2(13), 703.
12. Ahmadaliyevna, H. G. (2021). Talmeh or alluziya. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 772-779.
13. Ахмадалиевна, Х. Г. (2021). НАВОИЙ ВА СОБИР АБДУЛЛА. *ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI*, 1(2).
14. Хайдарова, Г. (2021). СОБИР АБДУЛЛА, ЧАРХИЙ ВА ХАБИБИЙ ФАЗАЛЛАРИДА ТАСВИР ВА ТАЛҚИН МАСАЛАЛАРИ. *FILOLOGIYA UFQLARI JURNALI*, 6(6).
15. Ahmadaliyevna, H. G. (2022). Interpretation of the Image of the Heart in the Poems of Habibi, Charkhi and Sabir Abdullah. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 6, 621-626.

16. Ҳайдарова, Г. А. (2022). XX аср ўзбек ғазаларининг вазн хусусиятига доир. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(6), 241-245.
17. Аҳмадалиевна, Ҳ. Г. (2022). СОБИР АБДУЛЛА, ЧАРХИЙ ВА ҲАБИБИЙ ҒАЗАЛИЁТИНИНГ ВАЗН ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИГА ДОИР. *Conferencea*, 47-49.